

Ionisation Constants of 3-Nitro Phthalic Acid in Mixed Solvents

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The thermodynamic ionisation constants of 3-nitro phthalic acid was determined by a method suggested by Speakman at 35°. By usual potentiometric method, using Henderson's equation pK_2 was calculated as a function of ionic strength and in various aquo organic mixtures like methanol-water, ethanol-water, isopropanol-water, acetone-water and dioxane-water mixtures. The mean radius of dianion in each one of these mixtures was calculated using Born's equation.

3-NITRO phthalic acid has been used as a chelating agent for different metal ions¹ like Mn, Co, Ni, Cu and Zn and their stability constants were calculated at low ionic strength. Recently Singh and Krishna Prasad² studied uranyl complexes with 3-nitro and 4-nitro phthalic acids. However, no work seems to have been done in mixed solvents and as such we thought it interesting to study the effect of ionic strength and dielectric constant on the ionisation process of 3-nitro phthalic acid.

The H_2A being dibasic acid will ionise as

Materials and Methods

The acid H_2A was a pure sample of Fluka make. The solvents Methanol, Acetone and Dioxane were of Analar quality while Ethanol was of 99.7 per cent purity. Iso propanol was purified by fractional distillation and the middle fraction distilling in the range 81.5° to 82° was collected and used. Potassium nitrate (AR) was used for adjusting the ionic strength. CO_2 free doubly distilled water was used for preparing the solutions.

pH measurements were made with ELICO pH meter Model LI-10 capable of reading upto ± 0.02 . The pH meter was standardised with buffers at pH 4.00 and 9.00. A dilute solution of the acid of known concentration (Ca. 2×10^{-2} moles liter⁻¹), was taken in a double wall jacketed cell through which water from a thermostat was circulated. The acid was titrated with standard alkali from a calibrated

5 ml. micro burette. In order to avoid dilution in the total volume of the solution, alkali used was much more concentrated than the acid. The pH values were noted after each addition of alkali and plot of pH against volume showed two distinct inflexions. However, since $pK_1 = 1.91$ and $pK_2 = 4.40^3$ are near each other, Henderson's equation could not be applied for determining pK_1 and hence only pK_2 was determined at different ionic strengths and in different aquo organic mixtures.

It was observed that pK_2 varies linearly with ionic strength, in the region $I \leq 0.2M$ at higher ionic strength the variation is very small and much confidence could not be placed on these values since the variation was of the same magnitude as experimental error, namely $\Delta pK_2 = \pm 0.02$ units. For lower region of ionic strength at 35° pK_2 is related to ionic strength by the equation

$$pK_2 = 4.23 - 1.70 I \quad (i)$$

and is shown in Fig. 1. The value of pK_1 and pK_2 at 35° in aqueous solution was also calculated by a method suggested by Speakmann⁴ and the values were 2.33 and 4.29 at 35°. The value of pK_2 at zero ionic strength from Henderson's equation 4.23 agrees fairly well with the independent calculation by Speakmann's method.

In aquo organic mixture pH values were corrected by use of Van Uitert and Hass⁵ equation,

$$-\log(H^+) = B + \log U_H \quad (ii)$$

where $B = pH$ meter reading and $U_H =$ conversion factor for the hydrogen ion concentration from the meter reading and in general will be a function of ionic strength and mole fraction of organic component. The values of pK_2 after correction by the use of equation (ii) in different aquo organic mixtures and at constant ionic strength of 0.1M and at temperature 35° is given in Table 1.

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TABLE I— pK_2 VALUES IN DIFFERENT AQUO ORGANIC MIXTURES AT $I = 0.1M$ AND $T = 35^\circ$

Wt. per cent of organic component :	Methanol-Water		Ethanol-Water			Isopropanol-Water			Acetone-Water			Dioxane-Water		
	E_s	pK_2	Wt.	E_s	pK_2	Wt.	E_s	pK_2	Wt.	E_s	pK_2	Wt.	E_s	pK_2
0.00	75.0	4.00	8.07	70.4	4.14	8.16	6.95	4.17	8.08	70.6	4.23	5.15	72.5	4.17
8.08	71.4	4.15	16.31	65.8	4.29	16.66	63.40	4.27	16.33	65.8	4.43	10.28	67.0	4.31
16.33	67.8	4.30	25.10	60.6	4.43	25.54	50.50	4.60	25.32	60.4	4.64	20.51	58.0	4.53
25.32	64.0	4.48	34.50	55.2	4.52	34.77	50.20	4.74	34.53	54.8	4.90	30.80	50.0	4.91
34.53	59.6	4.62	44.10	49.6	4.77	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

Fig. 1. Plot of pK_2 versus I (Ionic Strength).

As can be seen clearly from the Table I, pK_2 varies with dielectric constant and the applicability of Born's equation

$$-\log \frac{sK_2}{wK_2} = \frac{e^2}{rKT \ln 10} \left[\frac{1}{E_s} - \frac{1}{E_w} \right] \quad (iii)$$

was tested. A plot of $-\log sK_2/wK_2$ against $1/E_s$ gave a fairly linear relationship, Fig. 2. The dielectric constant for different aquo organic mixtures

was taken from literature⁶. From the slope the value of mean radius of dianion was calculated as $r_{\text{methanol}} = 1.58A$, $r_{\text{ethanol}} = 2.20A$, $r_{\text{isopropanol}} = 2.20A$, $r_{\text{acetone}} = 1.47A$ and $r_{\text{dioxane}} = 1.96A$.

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Fig. 2. Plot of $-\log \frac{sK_2}{wK_2}$ versus $\frac{1}{\epsilon} \times 10^2$.

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